

PERFORMANCE MAPS OF TEXTILE STRUCTURAL COMPOSITES

Jenn-Ming Yang

Department of Materials Science and Engineering
School of Engineering and Applied Science
University of California, Los Angeles, CA 90024

and

Tsu-Wei Chou

Center for composite Materials
National Engineering Research Center
University of Delaware
Newark, DE 19716.

ABSTRACT

This paper provides a concise summary of the recent accomplishments in analyzing the performance of various textile structural composites, and introduces the concept of structure-performance maps. These maps provide the correlation of thermo-mechanical properties with the various combinations of reinforcement configurations, matrix types as well as reinforcing fibers. They can serve as an effective tool for assessing the merit of each reinforcement concept and guiding engineers in materials selection and design.

INTRODUCTION

The advancements of high performance two- and three-dimensional textile reinforcements have opened up significant new opportunities in improving the properties of advanced composite materials for structural applications. Textile preforms include various two-dimensional biaxial and triaxial woven fabrics, multidirectional woven fabrics, knitted fabrics as well as various two-dimensional and three-dimensional braided structures (Fig. 1) [1]. These fabric architecture can be produced by various innovative weaving, knitting, and braiding techniques. The attractive features of these novel fiber architecture include improvements in damage tolerance and reliability, flexibility in fiber placement and fabric construction, and capability of near-net-shape design and fabrication. Additionally, fiber hybridization

allows considerable design flexibility in meeting the requirements of advanced high performance composites. Composites of high performance textiles reinforced polymer, metal, and ceramic matrices have found uses, or are being evaluated, in numerous electronic (such as printed circuit boards), automobile, and aircraft applications.

The potential of using high performance textile composites in structural applications has promoted extensive modeling and characterization efforts aiming at relating mechanical performance to the fabric structure of composites. Significant progress has been accomplished by Chou and coworkers [2-23] in establishing the constitutive relations and modeling the strength and failure behavior, as well as experimentally characterizing the performance and durability of these novel textile composites in polymer and metal matrices. The purpose of this paper is to integrate the results of extensive studies in the modeling and characterization of thermo-elastic properties and strength behavior of various two-dimensional (2-D) and three-dimensional (3-D) textile structural composites. Through the construction of structure-performance maps, the relative effectiveness and uniqueness of various textile reinforcement concepts can be assessed.

II. THEORETICAL MODELING

The theoretical basis of this study is briefly summarized as follows. Comprehensive discussion of the analytical modeling of the textile composites can be found in Reference 1.

A. Biaxial woven fabric composites [2-10]

Three analytical models have been developed to examine the thermo-mechanical properties of woven fabric composites. These are the "mosaic model", "crimp model", and "bridging model." The mosaic model treats the fabric composite as an assemblage of asymmetrical cross-ply laminates. The classical laminate theory is employed to derive the bounds of elastic moduli of fabric composites. The crimp model is a modification of the mosaic model and takes into account the effect of fiber undulation and continuity. A threadwise strip of the fabric composite forms the basis of the analysis, and the classical laminate theory is applied to each infinitesimal piece of the strip. The bridging model is further developed, particularly for satin weave composites, where the interlaced regions are not connected. The central portion of the unit cell in the bridging model represents the undulated fiber region, and it has lower in-plane stiffness than that of the surrounding regions with straight threads. Such regions with straight threads, therefore, carry higher loads and act as bridging zone for load transfer.

Analytical studies have been performed on the constitutive relations of both hybrid and non-hybrid fabric composites based upon the above physical models. Theoretical predictions are made for the elastic constants, in-plane thermal expansion and thermal bending coefficients, non-linear elastic behaviors, knee behavior and

strength of fiber composites with a wide range of reinforcement forms.

B. Triaxial woven fabric composites

In the case of 2-D triaxial woven fabric composites, an analytical method has been developed based upon the geometrical characteristics of the fabric construction. Triaxial woven fabric composites, with three sets of yarns interlaced with one another at 60° angles, offer improved isotropy and higher in-plane shear rigidity than that of biaxial woven fabric composites.

In the modeling process, the triaxial fabric composite is considered as composed of three impregnated, undulated yarn bundles oriented in $0^\circ/\pm 60^\circ$ directions. The concept of "crimp model" described above is extended to analyze the properties of each undulated bundle (Fig. 2). The overall thermo-elastic properties of the triaxial woven fabric composite can be obtained by summing up the contribution from each of the undulated composite bundle. This analytical methodology can be easily extended to analyze the performance of other triaxial fabric constructions such as staffed basic weave (which has an additional laid-in yarn in the fill direction), and 2-D braided composites.

C. Multilayer multidirectional warp-knit (MMWK) fabric composite

Recently, the methodology for analyzing the elastic properties, nonlinear deformation and strength behavior of multilayered multidirectional warp knit fabric composites has been established. The laminate construction for the MMWK fabric composite is composed of four yarn systems, weft yarns (0°), warp yarns (90°), and bias yarns held together by a fine denier stitching yarn system through the thickness of the fabric. The bias yarn placement can be arranged in either linear or nonlinear (wavy) insertion. The unit cell of the composite in the present study after matrix impregnation is then idealized as composed of four laminae stacking together (Fig. 3), i.e., 0° , 90° and two wavy laminae. The methodology developed by Takahashi and Chou [24] can be readily applied to obtain the effective properties of the in-phase sinusoidal composite laminae. Finally, the classical laminate plate theory is applied to obtain the overall thermo-elastic properties of the MMWK fabric composite. The analytical methodology can also be extended to analyze other knitted fabric constructions including laid-in yarn systems.

D. Three-dimensional braided composites

In the case of 3-D braided composites, two analytical methods have been established: fiber interlock model and fiber inclination model for predicting their thermo-elastic properties, as well as nonlinear deformation and strength behavior (Fig. 4). The unit cell adopted for the "fiber interlock model" is composed by two types of fiber structures: the base-line structure formed by fibers along three mutually orthogonal directions and the interwoven or braided structure composed of zig-zagging

fibers not orthogonal to one another. In the modeling process, the elastic strain energy due to fiber bending, extension and compression over the region of fiber interlocking are taken into account. The "fiber-inclination model" treats the unit cell of the 3-D braided composite as an assemblage of inclined unidirectional laminae. The classical laminate plate theory again forms the basis of the analysis. Theoretical predictions have been made of composite thermoelastic properties as functions of fiber spatial orientation, fiber volume fraction and braiding parameters. The "fiber inclination model" has also been extended to include the prediction of the nonlinear deformation and strength behavior of 3-D braided composites.[1]

III. PERFORMANCE MAPS

In order to assess the capability of various reinforcement configurations with different fiber and matrix combinations, parametric studies have been performed based upon the above analytical methods. Several types of reinforcement concept are investigated: biaxial woven fabrics, triaxial woven fabrics, 2-D and 3-D braided structures, 3-D orthogonal constructions, multilayered multidirectional warp knit fabrics as well as various nonwoven structures. The geometric parameters under consideration include, for instance, weaving or knitting patterns and braiding angles. The fiber materials evaluated in Ref [20] are glass, Kevlar, boron, graphite, silicon carbide and aluminum oxide. Matrix materials include various thermoset and thermoplastic polymers, metals as well as ceramic materials.

The graphite/PEEK composite is selected to demonstrate the effectiveness of the performance map. The structure-performance map of E_x vs. E_y for graphite/PEEK composite with various textile reinforcement geometries is shown in Fig. 5. The properties of various unidirectional angle-ply laminate composites are also listed for comparison. The fiber-volume fraction of all the composite systems is assumed to be 60%. The unique characteristics of each reinforcement concept is summarized as follows. The 2-D biaxial woven fabric composite can provide balanced in-plane thermo-elastic properties within a single ply. They behave similar to 0/90 cross-ply laminae, although the fiber weaviness tends to reduce the in-plane efficiency of the reinforcements. As the fabric construction changes from plain weave to 8-harness satin, the frequency of crimp due to fiber cross-over is reduced, and the fabric structure approaches that of 0/90 cross-ply laminate. The in-plane shear resistance of the biaxial fabric composites is poor.

The triaxial fabric composite, with the yarns arranged in three instead of two directions, provides a quasi-isotropic behavior within a single ply. They behave similar to $0/\pm 60^\circ$ angle-ply laminate. The effect of yarn crimp also reduces the in-plane efficiency of the reinforcement as in the case of biaxial fabric composites. The introduction of an additional straight laid-in fill yarn system will enhance the axial stiffness and strength. The in-plane shear rigidity of triaxial fabric composite is superior to that of the biaxial fabric composite. The elastic properties of the MMWK fabric composite are similar to those of the $0/90/\pm\Theta$ angle-ply laminate composite.

The unique characteristics of this novel reinforcement concept are the capability of introducing yarns in multiple directions, multilayers in an integrated manner, high level of yarn-to-fabric translational efficiency as well as good in-plane shear resistance. As a result, knitted fabric constructions can be tailored to meet various performance requirements ranging from complete directional stability to engineered directional elongation.

The elastic properties of 3-D braided composites also show a strong dependence on fiber orientation as those of the angle-ply lamiantes. Three-dimensional braided composites have demonstrated good in-plane properties, which is comparable to those of unidirectional angle-ply with the same range of fiber orientation. The longitudinal Young's moduli of the 3-D braided composites with braiding angles ranging from 15-35°, are better than those of the 2-D woven fabric, triaxial fabric and MMWK fabric composites. But, the transverse Young's moduli are lower and the major poisson's ratio are higher than those of the 2-D woven fabric composites. The 3-D braided composite also provides a unique capability in enhancing through-the-thickness properties by providing reinforcements along the thickness direction. The elimination of the interlaminar surfaces in braided structures is responsible for enhancing the damage tolerance and impact resistance.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The methodology for predicting the performance of various woven, knitted and braided textile structural composites has been successfully developed. These analytical methods provide the basis for evaluating the relative performance of various types of textile structure composites.
2. The performance of these novel textile reinforced composites has been integrated into comprehensive structure-performance maps. These maps can serve as an effective tool for assessing the merit of each reinforcement concept and guiding engineers in composites selection and design.

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Fig. 1 Various forms of woven, knitted, and braided textile reinforcements [1].

Fig. 2 The unit cell of triaxial fabric composite.

Fig. 3 The unit cell of MMWK fabric composite.

Fig. 4 Fiber inclination model [1].

Fig. 5 E_x and E_y for graphite/PEEK composites.

- : Angle-ply laminate
- : 2-D woven fabric
- : MMWK fabric, $c = A/\lambda$
- : 3-D braided